

SPARROW

SOLID PREPAREDNESS AND RESILIENCE
FOR ROBUST OPERATIONS DURING
DISASTER WILDERNESS

Deliverable: D1.4

Data Management Plan – 1

Work Package: 1

Project Management and Coordination

28 February 2025

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WP1 – Project Management and Coordination

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ABSTRACT	The initial version of this deliverable will provide an overview of the data generated during the project. It will categorize the data based on its confidentiality, ethical treatment, potential for open sharing, and format and standardization. Additionally, it will outline guidelines for managing all generated data in accordance with the categorization and the European Commission’s ethical framework.		

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Executive summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is an integral component of the SPARROW project, whose primary objective is to ensure a commitment to managing the entire lifecycle of data. Consequently, the project is committed to identifying, designing, and implementing the most effective practices for data management in accordance with the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) principles.

The proposed DMP serves as an introduction to the project's approach to managing research data within the context of a longer development strategy. As such, this document provides a comprehensive overview of the measures that the project anticipates implementing to curate, store, disseminate, and secure the data collected, processed, and/or generated during the project's duration and beyond.

1. Introduction

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is an essential part of the project, which ensures a commitment to implement the best practices for data management. The DMP provides a comprehensive overview of the measures that the project will adopt to curate, store, process, disseminate, and secure the data collected or generated throughout the project's lifespan and beyond. In essence, this deliverable encapsulates a long-term data management strategy within the project's context.

The DMP evolves as the project develops and will be reviewed continuously for fine-tuning in accordance with the data collected or generated to reflect important changes that may occur, such as new consortium policies or external factors.

This deliverable is organized into seven distinct sections. Section 2 provides an overview of the data type, format, and nature of data to be collected or generated, along with their relationship to the project's objective. It also outlines the origin of the data and the anticipated data usage. Section 3 describes the data management approach that adheres to the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) principles. Section 4 focuses on the management of personal data and other research outputs, Section 5 details the necessary resources, including expert personnel, equipment, and associated costs, for the project. Section 6 addresses the ethical implications that may arise from the generation, collection, or usage of the managed data. Finally, section 7 presents any other relevant considerations pertaining to the project data.

2. DATA Summary

2.1. Purpose of the Data Collection / Generation / Re-use

In this project, a diverse range of data types will be collected, generated, and reused to accomplish multiple objectives. Initially, data will be gathered for administrative purposes to ensure accurate records of project management, compliance, and stakeholder engagement. Additionally, data will be collected for analysis and simulation purposes, supporting the formulation and testing of hypotheses and enabling the modeling of interdependent system to predict potential outcomes. Experimentation purposes will be addressed through the generation of data via field-tested pilot studies conducted in three distinct European Union member states (i.e., Cyprus, the Czech Republic, and Greece), thereby enhancing the robustness of our findings. Furthermore, compilation purposes will be achieved by integrating all collected data into a comprehensive dataset, facilitating deeper analysis and future research endeavors. To support communication objectives, research findings will be disseminated through reports, presentations, and publications tailored to diverse audiences, including policymakers and the public. Collectively, these efforts will ensure that the data is relevant, robust, and instrumental in achieving the project’s overarching objectives.

2.2. Data Origin

The SPARROW research data can originate from various sources as highlighted in Table 1.

Table 1: Data Origin

Data Origin	Description
Observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Captured in real-time, typically outside the lab• Tools: Surveys, focus groups, interviews, etc.
Experimental	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Typically generated in the lab or under controlled conditions• Tools: Analytical studies in laboratory environment
Simulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Machine generated from test models• Tools: Mathematical modelling and simulation in MATLAB, Python etc.
Derived / Compiled	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Generated from existing datasets• Tools: Data Processing (Excel, MATLAB, Python, etc.)

2.3. Data Description

During the SPARROW project, data will be generated for administrative and communication purposes. Additionally, data will be collected and/or generated for experimentation and analysis purposes, thereby facilitating the implementation of the relevant Work Packages. In particular, Task 3.1 (T3.1) focuses on gathering and utilizing data to create a virtual representation of the cities

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involved in the use cases (Nicosia, Pilsen, Trikala). This includes data on critical infrastructure, demographics, mobility patterns, 3D spatial representations, emergency support assets, and risk and vulnerability assessments. The collected datasets will support various SPARROW modules such as scenario building, vulnerability assessment, decision support, interdependency modeling, and traffic rerouting. A simplified overview of the collected/generated data is presented in Table 2.

A detailed representation of the data inventory is presented in Table 4 in the appendix (represents only the features of the dataset inventory). The detailed data inventory will be updated continuously by the partners throughout the project in the Summary of Dataset document located in the project SharePoint ([Dataset Inventory SPARROW.xlsx](#)).

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Table 2: Simplified Overview of the Datasets in SPARROW

Dataset Name	Short Description	Data Format	Data Collection Method	Dataset Classification	Metadata Standard	Expected Volume / Size	Work Package	Dataset Owner (Partner)
Project Mailing List	Mailing List with all the contact details of the partners involved in the project	.csv or .xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	CERIF	1 MB	WP1	UCY
External Stakeholder Mailing List	List of recipients of the newsletter and other information and project dissemination material (compliant to GDPR)	.csv or .xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	CERIF	1 MB	WP1	UCY
Social media usage stats	Analytics of the social media accounts	.xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	Dublin Core	1 MB	WP1	UCY
STC Meeting Minutes	The minutes taken during Scientific & Technical Committee meeting	.pdf, .docx, .doc	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO 23081	1 MB	WP1	UCY
Public Deliverable Reports	Project Deliverables	.pdf, .docx, .doc	Derived/Compiled	Public	SIMS	10 MB	ALL	Consortium

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Restricted Deliverable Reports	Project Deliverables	.pdf, .docx, .doc	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	SIMS	10 MB	ALL	Consortium
Surveys after communication events	Anonymous survey results after the organization of events	.csv or .xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	Dublin Core	1 MB	WP1	UCY
IP disclosures	List of the IP generated as part of the project	.xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	Dublin Core	1 MB	WP1	Consortium
Consents for social studies	Informed consents for the social study	.pdf, .docx	Compiled	Restricted	DDI	10 MB	WP1	UCY
Telecommunication Base Station	Telecommunication towers (base stations) coordinates, services, technical parameters (power consumption, transmission, antenna height, coverage area, daily customer count), etc.	.json	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	Dublin Core	5 MB	WP3	UCY
Hazard Scenarios	Natural hazard scenarios around the chosen region of study	.csv or .xlsx or .json	Simulation	Restricted	ISO 19115	100 MB	WP3	UCY
ECOMAPP user provided data	Citizen status, provisions, threat	.json or .xml	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO/IEC 19944	1 MB	WP4	CTL

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	perception, health info, and immediate needs cover safety, essentials, risk assessment, medical details, and urgent aid.							
ECOMAPP device & usage data	Battery, brightness, and connectivity data optimize power use, recommend adjustments, and enable peer-to-peer or WiFi-based communication.	.json or .xml	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO/IEC 30141	1 MB	WP4	CTL
ECOMAPP location data	GPS, movement, and safe zone data assess risk, track evacuation, and locate nearby shelters or resources.	.json or .xml	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO 19115	100 MB	WP4	CTL
ECOMAPP communication and networking data	Offline messaging, emergency requests, and check-ins enable communication, distress signaling,	.json or .xml	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	Dublin Core	10 MB	WP4	CTL

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	and status sharing during network outages.							
ECOMAPP crisis & environmental data	Emergency alerts, crowdsourced reports, and disaster profiling gather crisis data, track hazards, and adapt recommendations in real time.	.json or .xml	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO 22320	10 MB	WP4	CTL
ECOMAPP security & compliance data	Consent logs and anonymized analytics ensure privacy compliance and enhance app performance.	.xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	DDI	1 MB	WP4	CTL
Data Related to Emergency Communication Devices (EMER-5G; EMPEER; ECOMAPP; SEDs)	Security, compliance, algorithms, data handling, and technical documentation.	.xlsx	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	DDI	1 MB	WP1	LIF
Regulatory Compliance Data	Emergency communication regulations in participating countries	.doc or .pdf	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO 22320	1 MB	WP1	LIF
Traffic model	A macroscopic or mesoscopic traffic model includes the street	.json	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	ISO 14825	100 MB	WP5	SITMP

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	network, traffic generators, and an origin-destination (OD) matrix.							
Vulnerability model	VASE delivers dynamic, predictive CI vulnerability analysis, integrating interdependencies, cascading effects, and simulations for better decision-making.	.json	Derived/Compiled	Restricted	DDI	100 MB	WP5	RG

3. FAIR Data

This section describes how SPARROW complies with the FAIR data management principles, as outlined below:

3.1. Data Findability

In SPARROW, data will be stored, managed, and described in a manner that maximizes its discoverability and identifiability. This will facilitate interoperability and data reuse, always in accordance with data accessibility restrictions.

Specifically, three methodologies will be employed to achieve the discoverability and identifiability of data: (a) adhering to strict naming conventions and metadata for each data item, (b) utilizing data management tools (e.g., software versioning), and (c) organizing data in a searchable folder structure.

Strict naming conventions will be consistently applied regardless of the data's location. Data management tools will be utilized to provide appropriate data grouping and metadata descriptions, thereby enhancing data searchability. Finally, data will be sorted in searchable folder structures based on their data type and the intended data usage.

3.2. Data Accessibility

3.2.1. Data Classification

SPARROW implements a multi-level access protocol to organize the procedures by which data can be stored and accessed by project members and the public. Three sensitivity levels will be utilized to classify data according to their access privileges: public, restricted, or confidential and its description is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Data Classification

Data Classification	Description
Public	Open data, which is considered public knowledge, is accessible to all individuals. This data can be found on websites, materials posted for download, open access links to cloud documents, Zenodo repositories, and other similar platforms.
Restricted	Restricted data is accessible to all or a subset of SPARROW members.
Confidential	Confidential data are restricted data that contain information and material, the unauthorized disclosure of such data could jeopardize the fundamental interests of the partners, their countries, or the European Union. Additional data security mechanisms, such as encryption, are required.

3.2.2. Data Storage

Any security measures put in place should aim to ensure that the following is **TRUE**:

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1. Access to, modification, disclosure, or deletion of the data is restricted to authorized personnel. It is imperative to note that these personnel are bound by the scope of their authorization and shall not exceed its boundaries.
2. The data in possession is accurate and complete in relation to the purpose for which it is being processed.
3. The data remains accessible and usable. If personal data is accidentally lost, altered, or destroyed, the relevant partner should be able to recover it, thereby preventing any damage or inconvenience to the concerned individuals or partners.

These are referred to as “confidentiality, integrity, and availability” and are part of the obligations under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

SPARROW utilizes an internal cloud repository (Microsoft SharePoint) to facilitate the secure and proper storage of the data requirements of the consortium. Furthermore, SPARROW has published a website (<https://sparrowproject.eu/>) to showcase the project’s details, including the details of the pilots, the partners, project updates via news, and the dissemination of public data and results in the form of publications to society.

3.2.3. Open Knowledge Portal

A primary objective is to facilitate broader access to research assets (i.e., scientific publications, research data, and software code) whenever feasible, while upholding academic integrity and commercial practices. The extensive dissemination of the project’s research assets will be made available, whenever possible, through the *SPARROW Open Knowledge Portal*. This platform will enable their verification and re-use by the broader community.

The *SPARROW Open Knowledge Portal*, which hosts and manages all the Open Access research assets produced during SPARROW, will be hosted on Zenodo¹, an online platform for managing open access and open research data. Zenodo is a data repository maintained by CERN and is now integrated into OpenAIRE, an EC-supported tool that facilitates the connection of publications to funded projects. Zenodo can accommodate research items such as journal/conference papers, presentations, posters, videos, code (linked with GitHub), and other data formats. Documents hosted on Zenodo are uniquely identified through a dedicated Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and can be linked to internal data or external data sources (e.g., on arXiv).

3.3. Data Interoperability

The collected and/or generated data will be stored in a format that facilitates its utilization across various computing platforms. To achieve this, formats that adhere to open standards will be employed, such as .pdf, .csv, .xml, and .json. This ensures compatibility with different software applications. Additionally, the data will be accompanied by appropriate metadata. In instances where the data follows a non-standardized format, explicit documentation will be provided for the dataset, detailing the parsing methodology. The adoption of open standards, metadata, and documentation will enable data utilization at all levels, promoting interoperability and facilitating reusability.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

3.4. Data Reusability

3.4.1. Re-Use Mechanisms

Licenses to be considered when releasing open research data and / or code, are described below.

Most typical options for data licensing include:

- Creative Commons License (CC)²
 - The CC License can have additional attributes, such as BY-attribution (BY), No-Derivatives (ND), Non-Commercial (NC), Share-Alike (SA) and combinations.
 - e.g. CC-BY: lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon a work, even commercially, if they credit the author for the original creation.
 - Wizard to select CC license: <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
- European Union Public License (EUPL) v1.2³
 - The only EU-approved copyleft license, translated in all EU languages and ratified by all EU countries.
 - Compatible to CC-BY-SA
 - Can be used for both code and documents as well

Most typical options for software licensing include:

- European Union Public License (EUPL) v1.2
- BSD (e.g., typically used by MathWorks for MATLAB community code)
- GPL, MIT etc.

3.4.2. Intellectual Property

The Intellectual Property (IP) strategy and policies will be covered in detail in deliverable D7.3 and D7.4.

² <https://creativecommons.org/>

³ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/community/eupl/news/understanding-eupl-v12>

4. Resource Allocation, Roles and Responsibilities

4.1. Scientific Coordinator

The Scientific Coordinator, Dr. Mathaios Panteli (UCY), is responsible for the following key tasks: (i) Serving as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority (European Commission), (ii) Facilitating communication between the project, beneficiaries, and the European Commission, (iii) Chairing the General Assembly and the Scientific and Technical Committee, (iv) Monitoring the progress of all research activities across Work Packages 2-6, (v) Promoting a multidisciplinary and innovative research environment among the partners, and (vi) Ensuring that the research results meet the highest quality standards.

4.2. Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator is Dr. Christos Laoudias (UCY), whose responsibilities and key tasks are to: (i) Organize the General Assembly and the Scientific and Technical Committee meetings – Prepare the agenda, coordinate meeting logistics, and produce written minutes that need to be approved; (ii) Monitor obligation compliance and manage administrative tasks – Maintain the contact list, collect, review, and submit reports, deliverables, financial statements, and other required documents to the funding agency. Handle financial issues, ensure efficient collaboration and communication among partners, resolve conflicts, and manage project risks; (iii) Supported by the Management Support Team – Oversee and delegate administrative, financial, and reporting tasks to the team, ensuring smooth day-to-day operations. The Management Support Team assists in compiling reports, tracking deadlines, preparing financial statements, maintaining project documentation, coordinating logistics for meetings and events, and ensuring compliance with funding agency guidelines. Additionally, the team provides support in handling inquiries from project partners and external stakeholders, facilitating internal communication, and managing document archiving; and (iv) Organize meetings and communicate the suggestions of the External Experts Advisory Board – Schedule and facilitate discussions with external experts, gather their feedback, and ensure their recommendations are conveyed effectively to the project consortium.

4.3. Technical Coordinator

The Technical Coordinator, Ms. Christina Michailidou (CTL), is responsible for facilitating communication between the Project Coordinator and the WP/Task leaders. Additionally, she is tasked with ensuring the appropriate monitoring of the technical aspects of the project, in accordance with the implementation plan.

4.4. Innovation Manager

The Innovation Manager is Mr. Daniel Van Lerberghe (EXUS). His responsibilities and key tasks are to: (i) Monitor and document the production of IP within the project, (ii) Review publications so that no unintended disclosures are made, while appropriate measures are taken for the production of IP where applicable and desired (e.g., via patent), (iii) Manage the foreground IP created within the project and background IP brought to the project by the partners, and (iv) Make suggestions to all

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WPs on how to align adoption of the research results to future innovations which are suitable for FR and others.

4.5. Data Manager

The Data Manager, Dr. Christos Kyrkou (UCY), is responsible for maintaining the project's data management plan. This plan ensures the appropriate processing of data generated throughout the process, including the safe storage, handling of personal data, and the dissemination of FAIR open data.

4.6. Communication Manager

The Communication Manager is Mr. Marios Stavrou (REACT), who is responsible for coordinating all activities related to the effective implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy of SPARROW.

4.7. Project Management Support Team

The Project Management Support Team is comprised of experienced staff proposed by the Scientific Coordinator and appointed by the Scientific and Technical Committee (STC). Its responsibilities and key tasks are to support the day-to-day management of the project, which includes: (i) communicating with the EC, (ii) resource planning and budget forecasting, (iii) record keeping and payments, deliverable submission, and other reporting, and (iv) provide information to external audits etc. Ms. Kalina Georgiades (UCY) will be coordinating this team.

4.8. Ethics Advisory Board

The Ethics Advisory Board will be led by Ms. Kristina Isakzay (LIF). Her responsibilities and key tasks are to: (i) Observe all activities of the SPARROW project from an Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects (ELSA) perspective– Ensure that all project activities align with ethical standards, legal requirements, and societal considerations, promoting responsible research and innovation; (ii) Supported by the Ethics Advisory Board – Work closely with the Ethics Advisory Board, which consists of experts in ethics, law, and societal impact. The Board provides guidance on ethical concerns, reviews compliance with ethical protocols, assesses potential ethical risks, and offers recommendations to ensure responsible research practices. The Ethics Advisory Board also assists in identifying best practices, ensuring transparency in ethical decision-making, and reviewing policies and procedures related to data protection, informed consent, and human participant research within SPARROW; (iii) Early identification of any deviations that may escalate to problems and suggest corrective measures to the STC – Monitor project activities for potential ethical, legal, or societal risks and proactively recommend corrective actions to the STC to prevent issues from escalating; and (iv) Evaluate the research studies conducted in SPARROW as well as the research outputs – Ensure that all research activities comply with ELSA requirements outlined in WP2, maintaining the highest standards of research integrity as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This includes preventing fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, or any other research misconduct.

4.9. Security Advisory Board

A Security Advisory Board has been established to address potential security vulnerabilities in the implementation of SPARROW. Its primary functions include: (i) Monitoring and reviewing project activities and deliverables that involve technical security aspects, (ii) Assessing whether project activities and outputs contain any sensitive information, (iii) Proposing timely measures to prevent the misuse of sensitive information, (iv) Providing consulting and advising on how to comply with specific security standards, and (v) Reviewing the outputs of project activities to ensure that security standards have been met at a high level and that no significant gaps exist that could compromise the exploitability and sustainability of project outputs.

5. Ethical Aspects

Ethical considerations are paramount to the development and execution of the DMP for the SPARROW project. In the context of ethical issues in social research, an informed consent procedure will be implemented, requiring extensive and comprehensive information to be provided to all participants. Therefore, prior to requesting consent, the researchers will ensure that all potential participants have received all the necessary information about the research, its objectives, and its execution details in writing.

A fundamental requirement is that all participants are aware that:

- they are free to withdraw at any point,
- their personal data will remain confidential and anonymous,
- the data will be analyzed, and results will be reported in such a way that it will not be possible to accidentally compromise privacy and anonymity.

It will be also clarified that SPARROW:

- does not involve research with human embryos & fetuses, human cells & tissues or animals,
- does not involve research with elements which can cause harm to the environment,
- does not involve dual-use research; it focuses exclusively on civil applications,
- does not have a potential misuse of data and material for unethical purposes,
- does not involve children or people from disadvantaged groups as this would not add value to the research results.

However, the project does involve:

- human participants in social science research,
- collection of certain personal data, which are relevant to the social study, such as ethics, reports, meeting minutes, informed consent templates.
- The project confirms the understanding and implementation of the:
- Data Protection Directive (95/46/EC) and the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (EU General Data Protection Regulation) - Article 32 on Security of personal data (Security of processing).
- ePrivacy Directive (2002/58/EC) - Article 5(3)

Furthermore, some of the key ethical measures in the context of the DMP for the project are outlined below, ensuring ethical integrity, fostering trust among stakeholders, and aligning with the European Union's commitment to responsible research and innovation.

5.1. Compliance with Legal Frameworks

All data management practices adhere to relevant legal restrictions on the use of various data types, ensuring compliance with the GDPR and other applicable laws.

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Data processing will be conducted lawfully, fairly, and transparently, with clear communication to participants about how their data will be used, stored, and shared. Personal data will only be collected for specified, legitimate purposes and limited to what is necessary for achieving those objectives. Efforts will be made to ensure data accuracy, with mechanisms in place to promptly rectify inaccuracies.

Retention of personal data will be restricted to the minimum duration required, with secure deletion processes for data no longer needed. Strong security measures, such as encryption and access controls, will protect against unauthorized access, breaches, or accidental loss. Accountability for GDPR compliance will be maintained by documenting data protection policies, assigning responsibilities, and regularly reviewing processes. Participants' rights will be upheld, including the ability to access, correct, or delete their data, restrict its processing, or receive it in a portable format. Additionally, explicit and informed consent will be obtained before processing personal data, with participants free to withdraw their consent at any time. These measures ensure ethical and legal integrity in the management and use of data throughout the project

5.2. FAIR Principles Implementation

The project is committed to implementing the FAIR principles while balancing ethical considerations. Particular attention is given to the responsible sharing and accessibility of data, ensuring that sensitive or personal information is adequately protected.

5.3. Ethics in AI Regulation

The DMP aligns with the broader EU regulatory framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI), ensuring the ethical design, implementation, and use of AI-based components. This includes evaluating potential biases, transparency in algorithmic processes, and promoting accountability to safeguard user trust.

5.4. Ethical Design and Participant Involvement

Throughout the development and deployment of SPARROW components in various use cases, ethical considerations are paramount. As necessary, ethical approvals are obtained, and informed consent from research participants is prioritized. Rigorous measures are implemented to safeguard participants' rights, privacy, and dignity throughout the research process.

5.5. Operational and End-User Requirements

The ethical implications of operational requirements and end-user restrictions are meticulously assessed. This encompasses addressing the specific needs of workers and aligning with management processes within participating industries and research centers. Efforts are made to strike a balance between innovation and ethical responsibility, thereby developing solutions that uphold users' rights and social norms.

5.6. Emergency Communication Devices

Legal and ethical requirements for emergency communication devices are meticulously addressed. These requirements encompass safety, accessibility, and the responsible use of data collected through such devices.

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5.7. Vulnerability and Risk Assessment

The project will include ongoing assessments to identify and evaluate potential vulnerabilities and risks related to data protection, privacy breaches, and ethical challenges. This includes monitoring the performance of AI systems to detect biases or security weaknesses and ensuring robust safeguards are in place. The assessments will involve regular reviews of processes and technologies to ensure compliance with ethical and legal standards.

5.8. Risk mitigation

To address identified risks, the project will implement proactive mitigation strategies, such as conducting regular security audits. A contingency plan will be maintained to respond swiftly to any breaches or ethical issues, ensuring minimal impact on participants and stakeholders while upholding the project's ethical and legal commitments.

6. Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable outlines the measures that SPARROW will implement to curate, store, disseminate, and secure the data collected, processed, and/or generated during the project’s duration and beyond. The DMP is a pivotal component of the project and, in essence, serves as a dynamic document that will be continuously monitored and updated at regular intervals.

The deliverable will undergo periodic reviews and updates to accommodate changes in the data collection methodologies.

The various Committees involved in data management (the Project Management and Stakeholder Team, the Data Manager, the Ethics Committee, and the Security Advisory Board) will provide support to the partners as required to implement the Data Management Strategy.

Appendix

Table 4: Dataset Inventory Format

Dataset Name	Short Description (Max 50 words)	Purpose of Dataset Collection	Data Collection Method	Dataset Owner (Partner)	Contact Person	Email Account	Dataset Format	Expected Volume / Size	Metadata Standard	Data Classification	Anonymization Needed?	Work Package	Expected Date(s) of Dataset Collection / Generation	GDPR Measures Implemented